

Selfie Taking Behavior and its Correlates among College Students of West Bengal**Raston Mondal¹, Sandip Kumar Ghosh², Debobroto Roy³, Sudip Ghosh⁴**¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College²Associate Professor, Department of Surgery, Burdwan Medical College & Hospital³Assistant Professor, Department of Gynae & Obst., Burdwan Medical College & Hospital⁴Statistician, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College

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Abstract**Background:** The tendency of taking own pictures through smart phone has turned into a madness among the people and it is more commonly seen especially among younger age groups. It has become so common that it is now been recognized as a separate disease entity.**Objectives:** This study aimed to find out the frequency & characteristics of selfie taking behaviour and to assess its correlates among the college students of Eastern India.**Materials and Methods:** This was a cross-sectional study carried out among 509 college students conducted from March, 2020 to May, 2020. Study population comprised of Science, Arts and Commerce undergraduate students from West Bengal. 12 colleges were approached, and 06 colleges agreed to participate in the study. Approval was taken from the respective colleges. Data was collected through distribution of online questionnaire. Finally, 509 college students responded.**Findings:** Study tracked down that mean narcissistic score of the undergrads was 5.12 (2.84) which is at moderate level. 9.44% of the understudies fall under the class of serious narcissistic highlights, 40.15% of the undergrads under moderate narcissistic highlights and 50.41% of the understudies under gentle narcissistic highlights. Narcissistic highlights had a huge relationship with number of selfies on a normal day, inclination of represent selfies, alter selfies prior to posting and untag themselves from bunch selfies. Posting of selfies on Facebook had critical relationship with narcissistic highlights at p level <0.05.**Conclusion:** Study inferred that greater part of the selfie taking undergrads had narcissistic manifestations. Medical services proficient has critical part in early screening of web clients and selfie takers so that fitting measures/mediations can be wanted to forestall mental side effects like narcissism in not-so-distant future.**Keywords:** Narcissism, Selfie, College Students, Selfie Taking Behavior.

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Introduction

Selfies have gotten immensely mainstream, and it is almost difficult to visit any online media website without seeing our companions' countenances in close-up. Named Word of the Year in 2013 by the Oxford English Dictionary, the expression "selfie" has gotten famous in the jargon of essentially every youngster and youthful grown-up in the innovative world. A selfie is characterized as "a photo that one has taken of oneself, commonly one taken with a cell phone or webcam and shared through social media".[1] For the Millennial Generation, the demonstration of taking selfies and generally speaking utilization of different online media stages are an indispensable piece of life. The Millennial Generation's solace with social stages has given this particular age bunch a more sure perspective on how online media may be influencing their lives. Studies, be that as it may, connect web-based

media use in youthful grown-ups to different conduct improvement issues. [2] Individuals love to take and post their selfies even they are in basic circumstances or any irritating environmental factors. For instance, when somebody met with a mishap, individuals take pictures, instead of calling rescue vehicle. In any case, they are known or obscure, they simply need to snap and post it. Certain individuals are more daring people to snap all the more intriguing selfies. They pick mountain edges, high cascades, treetops, railroad lines, with weapon and so on They are setting out to hazard their carries on with in any event, for straightforward selfie. [3] Research proposes that narcissistic attributes expanded among undergrads over ages because of the overuse of online media. [4] Self-love is an extreme reverence and ridiculous positive perspective on oneself and actual

appearance. A narcissist has an absence of respect for other people and exclusively focuses on what benefits them. [5] Recent investigations have recommended that posting selfies on informal communication locales has associated with self-detailing Self-love in youthful guys [6]. Furthermore, it was [7] found that the over-the-top utilization of sharing photos, statuses and companions in self-advancement corresponded with narcissist propensities utilizing the Narcissistic Personality Inventory scale. [8] It has investigated in detail that 55% of members accepted that narcissistic practices are ascending because of posting selfies on the Internet. It was [9] found that people who scored higher on narcissist qualities post more photographs on long range interpersonal communication locales. Selfies turned into a fascinating theme for analysts to contemplate and analyze on the grounds that since 2012, the pace of use of selfie expanded by 17,000%. [10] Certain investigations have detailed selfie taking being connected to psychopathologies, for example, pretentiousness, Self-love, and body dysmorphic jumble. [4]

Materials and Methods

Quantitative, enlightening, cross-sectional overview configuration was utilized to evaluate the narcissistic character highlights among selfie taking 509 helpfully chose understudies of Graduate, Post Graduate experts and Ph.D (17-30) from six college Hostel of West Bengal. Understudies who approached an advanced cell use and clicking selfies on normal premise were remembered for the examination. Following exploration apparatuses were utilized in the investigation:

Socio-demographic

It is utilized to gauge socio-segment subtleties of the undergrad. It has 11 things organized poll which were age, sexual orientation, religion, foundation, family type, conjugal status, family pay, pocket cash, program, class and long periods of formal schooling. The dependability was set up through test retest technique ($r=0.85$).

Selfie taking behavior questionnaire.

Selfie taking conduct poll was utilized to gauge the selfie taking conduct of understudies. Section of the apparatus contained 5 things identified with recurrence and nature of selfies and part B contained 6 things identified with reasoning and cycle of selfie taking. The things remembered for recurrence and nature of selfies are clicked selfies

or not, number of selfies on a normal day, sort of shot liked, inclination of selfies and prevailing feeling while at the same time clicking selfies. The things remembered for reasoning and cycle of selfie taking are purpose behind clicking selfies, transfer selfies on long range interpersonal communication destinations, inclination of represent selfies, inclination of long-range interpersonal communication locales, alter selfies prior to posting them and untag themselves from bunch selfies if not looking best. The dependability was set up through test-retest strategy ($r=0.84$).

Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI 16)

Narcissistic Personality Inventory (NPI 16) Narcissistic Personality stock (NPI 16) was created by Ames et al (2006) [11] and utilized in this stud to quantify Self-love of undergrads. It incorporate 16 sets of proclamations and the one that comes nearest to sentiments and convictions about oneself ought to be chosen. Most extreme conceivable score is 16 and least conceivable score is 0.

The got scores were arranged in five classifications: Non narcissistic highlights (0 score), gentle narcissistic highlights (score range 1-4), moderate narcissistic highlights (score range 5-8), serious narcissistic highlights (score range 9-12) and exceptionally extreme narcissistic highlights (score range 13-16). Complete organization time for this apparatus was roughly 7-8 minutes Reaction rate was high. Suitable clear and inferential insights was utilized to dissect information through SPSS (21) programming. p esteem <0.05 was considered as level of essentialness.

Results

Mean age of the understudy was 20.24 ± 1.65 years. Most extreme understudies were ladies (90.3%). Moreover, 7.2% of the undergrads were taking >15 number of selfies every day and wanted to took selfies with their companions (39.6%). Almost two third (67.28%) of undergrads favored gathering selfies with delight as predominant feeling (92.43%).

Having love clicking themselves was the most favored purpose behind clicking selfies (39.37%). In excess of two third (72.47%) of understudies transfer selfies on social locales ideally on WhatsApp (81.46%), More than half (64.21%) of undergrads once in a while alter their selfies prior to posting them and 42.65% of understudies never untag themselves from bunch selfie.

Table 1: Mean (SD) of Self lover of college students (N=509)

Variable	Minimum to maximum possible score	Mean (SD)	Maximum obtained score	Minimum obtained score
Self lover	0-16	5.12 (2.84)	12	0

Table 1 depicts that mean (SD) of narcissistic score was 5.12 (2.7) for the college students with range of 0-12. Hence it can be concluded that college students had non narcissistic features as the mean is below the middle point of score.

Table 2: Relationship of Self love with selfie taking behavior among college students (N=509)

Selfie taking behavior		Mean±SD	F/t value	p value	
Number of selfies on an average day	0-5	5.11±2.17	6.635*	0.001	
	6-10	5.29±2.32			
	11-15	6.39±1.36			
	>15	5.32±2.04			
Type of shot prefer	Head/face shot	5.41±1.95	2.41 ^{NS}	0.953	
	With your surroundings	5.18±2.14			
	Body shot	4.61±2.10			
	With your friends	5.45±2.65			
Preference of selfies	Group selfies	5.84±2.49	0.982 ^{NS}	0.634	
	Individual selfies	5.25±2.53			
Dominant emotion in most of selfies	Anger	4.86±2.61	0.981 ^{NS}	0.856	
	Joy	5.12±2.17			
	Sadness	5.34±1.95			
	Surprise	4.71±2.13			
	Other	2.83±1.44			
Reason for clicking selfies	Due to boredom	No	5.66±2.64	4.351*	0.000
		Yes	4.11±2.18		
	To message or upload it	No	5.46±2.48	0.453 ^{NS}	0.841
		Yes	5.39±2.41		
	Peer pressure	No	5.43±2.37	0.549 ^{NS}	0.873
		Yes	5.53±2.12		
	To boost my confidence	No	5.46±2.47	0.121 ^{NS}	0.494
		Yes	5.24±2.31		
	To attract attention	No	5.37±2.54	5.745 *	0.031
		Yes	4.92±2.44		
	The band wagon effect	No	5.41±2.24	4.379 ^{NS}	0.455
		Yes	5.26±2.33		
	I love clicking myself	No	5.24±2.19	3.346 ^{NS}	0.747
		Yes	5.76±2.43		
	To get compliments	No	5.41±2.92	1.650 ^{NS}	0.543
		Yes	5.78±2.66		
	Others	No	5.50±2.18	6.252 ^{NS}	0.413
		Yes	4.99±2.23		

NS= Nonsignificant, * = Significant

Table 3: Relationship of Self love with selfie taking behavior among college students (N=509)

Selfie taking behavior		Mean±SD	F/t value	p value	
Upload selfies on social media	Yes	5.53±2.14	0.948 ^{NS}	0.344	
	No	5.22±2.98			
Preference of act for selfies	Posting on social sites	5.35±2.26	4.542*	0.002	
	Send through instant messaging app	5.34±2.61			
	Keep as personal collection	5.10±2.48			
Social networking site preference	Whatsapp	No	5.13±2.68	2.457 ^{NS}	0.160
		Yes	5.62±2.23		
	Instagram	No	5.47±2.52	0.872 ^{NS}	0.459
		Yes	5.33±2.60		
	Snapchat	No	4.89±2.46	2.157 ^{NS}	0.290
		Yes	5.82±2.50		
	Facebook	No	5.74±2.35	3.457*	0.040
		Yes	5.86±2.21		
Others	No	5.64±	0.413 ^{NS}	0.874	

		2.42		
	Yes	5.28±3.67		
Edit selfies before posting	Yes	4.87±2.25	7.216*	0.001
	Sometimes	4.42±2.33		
	No	5.78±2.71		
Untag themselves from a group selfie if not looking best	Yes	4.83±2.63	3.412 ^{NS}	0.149
	Sometimes	5.29±2.34		
	No	5.63±2.41		

NS= Non-significant, * = Significant

Table 2 and 3 revealed that Self-love has significant relationship with number of selfies on an average day, preference of act for selfies and edit selfies before posting. College students who click more selfies and uploading them on social networking sites had more Self-love symptoms. College students who were editing selfies before posting had more Self-love symptoms.

Discussion

This examination, being one of only a handful not many in West Bengal (India) concerning selfie-taking among undergrads, brought some intriguing findings. Present study found that a 4.72% of the undergrads were taking >15 number of selfies every day and liked to take selfies with their companions (47.46%). In excess of two third (70.12%) of undergrads transfer selfies on social locales ideally on WhatsApp (74.36%). These findings are in accordance with an investigation led by Dutta et al [12] who announced that (40.23%) clicked 0–2 selfies in a day while (32.34%) clicked more than 4 selfies/day, (27.4%) of the populace clicked more than 10 selfies seven days. Hingerton [13] likewise revealed that 56.10% subjects post their selfies on social locales after editing. In this investigation, it was discovered that 9.44% of the undergrads had extreme narcissistic highlights, 40.15% of the undergrads had moderate narcissistic highlights and 50.41% of the undergrads had mellow narcissistic highlights. This finding is reliable with Bergman et al [9] who found that people who scored higher on narcissist qualities post more photographs on interpersonal interaction sites.

In the current investigation, undergrads detailed that they like to click shot with companions (41.3%), trailed by head/face selfies (38.3%), trailed by with their environmental factors (14.3%) and just 6% of the undergrads made body effort selfies. These discoveries were upheld by Saroshe [14] who revealed that 20% reacted with family, 68% said with companions, 1% with structures, 4% with creatures, 2% with vehicles, and 5% reacted none of the above. Majority (70%) of undergrads transfer selfies which are awesome, while 30% of the undergrads don't want to transfer selfies. These discoveries were upheld by Hingerton [13] detailed that 56.10% of the 82 subjects post their selfies and 43.90% of the members didn't post their selfies. Veena et al [15] and Gill [16] additionally revealed the comparable discoveries. This examination uncovered that Self-love has huge relationship with number of selfies on a normal

day, inclination of represent selfies and alter selfies prior to posting. Undergrads who click more selfies and transferring them on person to person communication locales had more Self-love side effects.

Undergrads who were altering selfies prior to posting had more Self-love manifestations. Likewise discoveries were accounted for by Amurao et al [17] that there is a positive straight connection between selfie conduct and the Self-love among females with $r = 0.84$ critical at $p < 0.05$.

Conclusion

Study reasoned that dominant part of the undergrads who were taking selfies with their advanced mobile phones and were transferring them on interpersonal interaction sites ideally on WhatsApp in the wake of altering them had more self-love manifestations. Lion's share of the undergrads had narcissistic highlights from mellow to extreme which might be an admonition sign. This study gives knowledge into the young's perspective towards selfies and Self-love.

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